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Research Article

**A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON CORRELATION OF LEVEL
OF OBESTATIN AND OBESITY**¹Dr. Umer Farooq, ²Dr. Khaliq ur Rehman, ¹Dr. Asma Parveen¹Holly family Hospital²Polyclinic Hospital, Islamabad**Abstract:**

Introduction: Obestatin was discovered by Zhang et al. in 2005, which is an anorectic peptide consisting of 23 amino acids and it is encoded by the same gene as ghrelin. The distribution of obestatin in human tissues is poorly understood. **Aims of the study:** The basic aim of the study is to find the correlation of level of obestatin and obesity. **Methodology of the study:** This study was conducted at Holly family hospital during 2018. The data was collected from 50 obese patients which was also suffering from heart and cholesterol diseases. Demographic factors were also asked to the student. Body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference (WC) were done for patients and controls as anthropometrical tests, while fasting serum glucose (FSG) measured using spectrophotometric technique. **Results:** Mean fasting obestatin levels was 0.450 ± 0.468 and 0.959 ± 0.889 respectively in hypertensive and normotensive obese and the difference of mean fasting obestatin levels between the both groups was statistically significant with p value 0.000. **Conclusion:** Obestatin plays very important role in obesity and it is directly correlated with blood glucose level. Furthermore, there was a clear relationship between obestatin and both BP and HOMA-IR, suggesting that obestatin might play a role in BP regulation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Obestatin was discovered by Zhang et al. in 2005, which is an anorectic peptide consisting of 23 amino acids and it is encoded by the same gene as ghrelin. The distribution of obestatin in human tissues is poorly understood. It has been showed by immuno fluorescence technique using specific antiserum against obestatin that there were obestatin immuno reactivity in small and large intestine, pancreas, hypothalamus and pituitary gland; in cells of gastric mucosa and myenteric plexus, and in Leydig cells of testis in rats. It has been suggested that obestatin suppresses appetite, reduces food intake, and it behaves as a physiological opponent to ghrelin [1]. However, the finding that obestatin opposes ghrelin's stimulatory effect has been questioned by later studies and some of the authors stated that obestatin and ghrelin have similar effects on appetite and food intake. Obesity is a pathological condition, which results from an imbalance between caloric intake and expenditure, and is characterized by excessive body fat accumulation, that has severe impact on life quality and life expectance due to the burden of associated co-morbidities. Recent data from the World Health Organization suggest that 11% of the world population (more than half a billion people) is obese, while 35% is overweighted [2]. Furthermore, the prevalence of obesity is continuously increasing worldwide, so revealing the patho mechanism and finding effective treatments have become urgent and essential. During the past decades much research has highlighted that neurotransmitter systems controlling appetite and feeding behavior, cognitive function, stress and reward behavior are strongly and reciprocally connected. Food intake is normally regulated by a homeostatic drive to restore energy balance, while in certain conditions hedonic or reward-based regulation favors the consumption of highly palatable, energy-dense foods [3].

Obestatin is a 23-acid metabolic peptide, derived from the preproghrelin gene which was isolated first from the rat stomach in 2005. However, obestatin is also expressed in other GI organs (pancreas, liver), adipose tissue, skeletal muscle, lungs, thyroid and mammary glands and testes, suggesting a

Table 01: Comparison of mean fasting obestatin levels between hypertensive and normotensive obese

Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
Hypertensive obese	57	0.450	0.468	0.000
Normotensive obese	57	0.959	0.889	

multifunctional role of it, which can act both centrally and peripherally. It was originally described as a direct antagonist of ghrelin with anorexigenic effect [4]. Both central and peripheral injection decreased food intake in a time and dose-dependent manner, body weight gain, and intestinal motility via the G-protein coupled receptor 39 (GPR39) a member of the GHSR family which was rapidly refuted as a receptor for obestatin by several studies [5]. To note, recent data suggest that obestatin may act through the GPR39 receptor in an autocrine/paracrine manner peripherally, namely as mitogenic factor in myoblasts and GPR39 could mediate the metabolic effects of obestatin in the adipose tissue and GI system [6].

Aims of the studyq21

The basic aim of the study is to find the correlation of level of obestatin and obesity.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This study was conducted at Holly family hospital during 2018. The data was collected from 50 obese patients which was also suffering from heart and cholesterol diseases. Demographic factors were also asked to the student. Body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference (WC) were done for patients and controls as anthropometrical tests, while fasting serum glucose (FSG) measured using spectrophotometric technique. Each serum sample was analyzed for obestatin hormone and fasting insulin using enzyme linked immune sorbent assay (ELISA).

Statistical analysis

SPSS analysis test was used in making a comparison of the two-tailed P value of the two groups with a significance set at $p < 0.05$. Results were considered to be of statistical significance if the two-tailed p-value was less than 0.05.

RESULTS:

Mean fasting obestatin levels was 0.450 ± 0.468 and 0.959 ± 0.889 respectively in hypertensive and normotensive obese and the difference of mean fasting obestatin levels between the both groups was statistically significant with p value 0.000.

Table 02: Comparison of mean fasting blood cholesterol levels between normal and obese patients

Group	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
Normal	57	206.42	44.420	0.644
Obese patients	57	202.39	48.344	

Mean fasting blood cholesterol level was 206.42 ± 44.420 and 202.39 ± 48.344 respectively in normal and obese and the difference was not statistically significant with p value 0.644.

DISCUSSION

Obestatin is an anorectic peptide consisting of 23 amino acids and it is encoded by the same gene as ghrelin hormone. Little is known about the effect of obestatin on reproductive system. In a recent study, it has been reported that obestatin can directly control functions of granulosa cells via stimulating proliferation and apoptosis of granulosa cells and progesterone secretion in pig ovaries [7]. With opposite effect to ghrelin, obestatin suppresses appetite and reduces food intake. Obestatin excites vagal afferent fibers, which resulted in an increased sense of satiety and weight gain can be prevented. In human studies, based on the finding that obestatin levels are higher in obese subjects compared to lean litter-mates suggests that the obestatin may have a role in the long-term regulation of body weight. Hormones and neuropeptides control and integrate the neuro circuits of metabolism, thirst, thermoregulation, and sleep overlapping in the hypothalamus. Accordingly, besides its peripheral effects, central actions of obestatin were also identified⁹. To note first, when administered ICV this peptide inhibited thirst in fed and fasted male rats, and pretreatment with obestatin also neutralized the dipsogenic effect of angiotensin II [8]. Furthermore, it was also suggested that the anorexigenic effect of this peptide is a consequence of the thirst inhibition, the so called dehydration anorexia.

The neurogenesis in the adult hippocampus involves the proliferation, migration and differentiation of progenitor cells. These processes are impaired by different conditions, such as hypoxia, addictive drugs, sustained exposure to stress among others, while certain hormones and growth factors promote the proliferation and survival of the hippocampal neurons.

Obesity has become a major public health problem throughout the world and at least one-third of Arabs are obese, and this figure is rising steadily despite increased interest in fitness. Excess fat accumulation promotes the development of insulin resistance, glucose intolerance and type 2 diabetes mellitus. The increasing prevalence of obesity is a serious health

concern. Obesity is known to be strongly associated with hypertension and other arteriosclerotic disease, but the pathogenic mechanisms linking hypertension and obesity have not been fully determined. The possible roles of obestatin and ghrelin in obesity and metabolic syndrome have been studied. Changes in the concentrations of these hormones, and in the ghrelin/obestatin ratio, may be risk factors for obesity and hypertension [9].

Obestatin levels were significantly reduced suggesting that the secretion of the Ghrelin and Obestatin is regulated in an opposing manner by the nutritional status. These findings suggest that obestatin could modulate endogenous Ghrelin actions, and have shown that obestatin may inhibit jejunal activity and may suppress gastric emptying activity.

CONCLUSION:

Obestatin plays very important role in obesity and it is directly correlated with blood glucose level. Furthermore, there was a clear relationship between obestatin and both BP and HOMA-IR, suggesting that obestatin might play a role in BP regulation.

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